

PARACHOR AND RING STRUCTURE. PART IV

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The parachor of benzene ring by the method of Gibling has been calculated and comes out to be practically zero.

Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299) has discarded Sugden's values for atomic and structural parachors and suggested his own values. However, his work is only limited to some of the aromatic homologous series. In this paper we have tried to calculate the value for benzene ring. E. C. denotes "expansion correction" and S. V. denotes "standard values" as calculated by us by his method. The observed values for the parachor of the substances are taken from "A list of Parachors" (*Brit. Assoc. Rep.*, 1932). The values are as recorded below.

TABLE I

Substance.	S.V.	E.C.	$P_{calc.}$	$P_{obs.}$	Mean diff %
Benzene	205.8	0.4	206.2	206-206.3	0.0
Toluene	243.4	0.6	244.0	245-246.9	-0.8
Ethylbenzene	283.2	0.8	284.0	283-284	+0.2
<i>n</i> -Propylbenzene	323.0	1.0	324.0	322-323.1	+0.4
<i>n</i> -Butylbenzene	362.8	1.3	364.1	361.7	+0.7
<i>n</i> -Amylbenzene	402.6	1.6	402.2	402.0	+0.5
<i>n</i> -Hexylbenzene	442.4	1.9	444.3	442.0	+0.5
Benzaldehyde	255.6	0.6	256.2	254-256.2	+0.4
Acetophenone	294.3	0.8	295.1	293.8	+0.5
Methyl benzoate	309.8	0.9	310.7	310.4	+0.1
Ethyl cinnamate	418.2	1.6	419.8	417.2	+0.6
Methyl cinnamate	378.4	1.4	379.8	373.9-385.2	+0.08
Diphenylmethane	416.2	1.7	417.9	414.5-419	+0.2
Benzophenone	427.3	1.8	429.1	428.2	+0.2
Benzil	478.2	2.2	480.4	480.8	-0.08
Xylene	281.9	0.8	282.7	283.3-284	-0.3
Mesitylene	318.5	0.9	319.5	320.5	-0.3
<i>p</i> -Ethyltoluene	320.8	0.9	321.7	320.8	+0.3
<i>p</i> -Cymene	358.4	1.2	359.6	357-360.7	+0.2
Tetramethylbenzene	356.2	1.2	357.4	355.6	+0.5

In the case of *cyclohexane* and *cyclohexanone* the following values are obtained :

Substance	S.V.	E.C.	$P_{\text{calc.}}$	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Mean dif. %
<i>cyclohexane</i>	238.8	0.55	239.35	239.3-241.8	-0.5
<i>cyclohexanone</i>	249.9	0.6	250.5	251.4	-0.3

The coincidence between calculated and observed parachors shows that the contribution of benzene ring towards parachor is practically negligible. In case of *cyclohexane* and *cyclohexanone* although the nature of the ring is slightly different (as there are no double bonds) yet there is a close agreement between calculated and observed values, indicating that contribution of six-membered ring towards parachor is practically zero. However, certain anomalies have also been observed as shown below.

TABLE II

Substance.	S.V.	E.C.	$P_{\text{calc.}}$	$P_{\text{obs.}}$	Mean dif. %
Dibenzylethane	456.0	1.9	457.9	449.8	+1.5
Diphenylpropane	495.8	2.3	498.1	484.5	+2.8
Pentamethylbenzene	393.8	1.5	395.3	390.0	+1.4

These anomalies may be due to slight inaccuracies in the determinations of parachors. The values for the observed parachor are in general smaller than the calculated values and hence the benzene ring, if it has any value, will be negative. By following general procedure, that is, by subtracting calculated values from mean observed values we get for parachor of benzene ring a value = (-0.55). This value when substituted gives smaller percentage error, in general below 0.5%. However the error possible in the observed values is almost 0.5% as suggested by Sugden. The error observed with parachor of six-membered ring = 0 is also of the same order of magnitude. It is interesting to observe that the benzene itself gives the ring value = 0.